

Practice Oriented Science: UAE – RUSSIA – INDIA

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CONTENTS

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

Social orientation in an efficient economy <i>Sutyagin Vladilen Vasilievich</i>	7
Problems of regulating territorial imbalances in economic growth in the Russian Federation <i>Ershova Natalya Anatoliyevna</i>	11
The concept of intellectual capital: analysis of existing approaches and new wording <i>Larin Sergey Nikolaevich</i>	18
Cognitive approach to knowledge management as tools for decision-making by economic entities <i>Larin Sergey Nikolaevich</i>	25
How to increase client loyalty to the company brand? <i>Kapitanov Egor Alekseevich</i>	32

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

Scientific and methodological problems of teaching students advanced technologies in group project training and their solution <i>Orlikov Leonid Nikolaevich</i>	41
Cultural approach and innovative pedagogical technologies in the professional training of future music teachers <i>Kolomoitsev Yuri Alekseevich</i>	48

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

Activities of the Russian imperial political agency in the Bukhara Emirate (1886-1917) <i>Klichev Oybek Abdurasulovich, Syzdykova Zhibek Saparbekovna</i>	54
Communication of the Russian Imperial Consulate General in Jerusalem with the local Jewish community in late nineteenth century <i>Georgi Daria Grigoryevna, Georgi Fedor Vadimovich</i>	62

THE CONCEPT OF INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL: ANALYSIS OF EXISTING APPROACHES AND NEW WORDING

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Annotation. *Currently, domestic economists clearly believe that the development of intellectual capital has a direct impact on increasing the competitiveness of Russian enterprises in the domestic and foreign markets. In the context of the negative impact of sanctions restrictions, this topic seems especially relevant. The article analyzes scientific research by various authors and existing approaches to defining the concept of intellectual capital. Its results showed that there is still no generally accepted formulation of the concept of intellectual capital. Many researchers in their works recognize intellectual capital as one of the most important elements of economic development, but offer different approaches to defining this concept and its economic essence. Based on the results of the analysis of existing scientific research, the authors proposed the most adequate formulation of the concept of intellectual capital to modern conditions.*

Keywords: *intellectual capital, intangible assets, knowledge generation, information technology, managerial and professional competencies.*

Introduction

At the present stage, the determining factors in the development of the world economy have become the generation of knowledge and the rapid expansion of the areas of application of information technologies. Today, it is these factors that have the greatest impact on the competitiveness of enterprises in all sectors of the economy. However, by themselves they cannot guarantee the successful development of the enterprise. This requires a combination of such conditions as the presence of intellectual capital with the necessary managerial and professional competencies, an optimal production structure and favorable opportunities for its practical use. These circumstances predetermined the emergence of new challenges that entailed the need to develop a new paradigm for the development of the world economy in a new objective reality, when the generation of knowledge and

information technologies becomes key factors that determine the availability of intellectual capital of enterprises. Despite the fact that a fairly large number of foreign and domestic scientists pay close attention to the study of the concept of intellectual capital and its economic essence, the scientific community has not yet formed a generally accepted approach to defining the concept of intellectual capital as the basis for ensuring the competitiveness of enterprises in modern conditions. In this regard, there is a need to conduct a study of existing approaches to defining this concept, revealing its economic essence and clarifying the formulation that generalizes these approaches and is adequate to the objective realities of the current stage of development of the world economy.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is to analyze modern approaches to defining the concept of intellectual capital, revealing its essence, and also to clarify, based on the results of the analysis, the formulation of this concept that is adequate to the features of the current stage of development of the world economy.

Materials and methods

The concepts of intellectual potential and intellectual capital were first introduced into scientific circulation in 1969 by the famous American economist of the 20th century J. Galbraith, who initially defined their meaning as products of “intellectual activity” [5]. But, since intellectual activity itself can be viewed from different points of view, and intellectual capital has become a relatively new form of manifestation of an enterprise’s capital, a number of other definitions of this concept have appeared in a fairly short period of time. At the same time, today in scientific theory and economic practice there are no sufficiently clear definitions of the concepts of intellectual potential and intellectual capital. Moreover, there are quite a lot of studies whose authors identify these two concepts.

Since this study will present an analysis of modern approaches to defining the concept of intellectual capital, in the future we will operate with this concept and its definitions, justified by foreign and domestic researchers within the framework of their proposed approaches.

Representatives of the knowledge-based approach to defining the concept of intellectual capital, S. Albert and K. Bradley, considered it as “the process of transforming knowledge and intangible assets into useful resources that provide competitive advantages to individuals, firms and nations” [15].

Representatives of the value approach defined intellectual capital as “a set of intangible assets that can be used to create value, and without which an enterprise cannot exist and develop its competitive advantages” [3]. At the same time, human capital, represented through the body of knowledge of the enterprise’s personnel, its managerial and professional competencies, skills and abilities to solve various production problems, as well as intellectual property and other market assets, were identified as the key components of intellectual capital.

Subsequently, these approaches were considered jointly by some authors. Thus, J. Daum defined intellectual capital as “structured knowledge and abilities based on connections that have the potential to develop and create enterprise value” [16]. Very close to this formulation was the definition of intellectual capital as a body of knowledge that can be converted into enterprise value [14, 17].

Representatives of the structural approach proposed to distinguish the following components as part of the intellectual capital of an enterprise:

- intellectual capital as qualities that characterize the enterprise’s personnel as a resource, provided that these qualities cannot be replaced by machines;
- social capital as the relationships that an enterprise establishes with its counterparties (clients, consumers, intermediaries, representatives, suppliers, partners, owners, creditors, etc.);
- organizational capital as a set of organizational decisions and production management technologies that cannot be reflected in the balance sheet of an enterprise [18].

Among domestic scientists, B.B. Leontyev made a great contribution to the development of the theory of intellectual capital. According to his definition, the intellectual capital of an enterprise should be considered as “the value of the total intellectual assets of the enterprise, including its intellectual property, managerial and professional competencies and intellectual abilities of personnel, information knowledge bases and relations with the enterprise’s counterparties” [9]. At the same time, one of the main functions of intellectual capital, in his opinion, is “accelerating the growth of the mass of profits through the formation and implementation of the knowledge and relationship systems necessary for the enterprise, which contribute to increasing the efficiency of its production activities” [9].

Modern domestic researchers in their works reveal the features of the practical use of intellectual capital as one of the key factors of production, and also develop models for assessing and managing its development. Thus, the main directions of the practical use of intellectual capital in relation to its significance in the innovative development of enterprises, the analysis of definitions of the category of intellectual capital and the concept of the level of intellectual capital are disclosed in [13]. For this purpose, a decomposition-aggregate method for measuring intellectual capital was developed, as well as a three-stage model for managing the level of intellectual capital and its use.

Intellectual capital was defined in [11] as “a key factor of production that determines the efficiency of economic activity in a post-industrial society and represents the implementation of knowledge and information as economic resources in sectors of social production.”

A stochastic model for determining the integral indicator of an enterprise’s intellectual capital as the main factor influencing the level of its competitiveness

is presented in [2]. It is proposed to use the level of intellectual capital of an enterprise as the main component of its competitiveness. This indicator was determined on the basis of the composition of the characteristics of the enterprise's personnel, which included the amount of certain knowledge, managerial and professional competencies, skills and abilities in production activities. The existence of a probabilistic relationship between competitiveness and the level of intellectual capital has been established. Mathematical dependencies of competitiveness and intellectual capital have been identified, a model has been built that allows us to study the processes of learning, acquiring professional qualities and, thereby, adequately manage the competitiveness of an enterprise and improve product quality in the conditions of import substitution.

Intellectual capital is defined as the total knowledge of all employees of an enterprise, which can be converted into value and ensure its competitiveness in work [6]. As we can see, even in this definition, there is a lack of necessary completeness and clarity.

Approaches to assessing intellectual capital and its components - structural, client and human capital are considered in work [1]. The problems of quantitative assessment of human, client and organizational capital are identified. A method for assessing the economic potential of an enterprise is proposed, based on the development of an income approach to assessing its market value, taking into account the influence of intellectual capital.

The role of intellectual capital from the perspective of the concept of enterprise value management is shown in [10]. The author has explored approaches to defining the concept of intellectual capital and its components. The essence of intellectual capital as a resource, potential and result, which are simultaneously stages of production and reproduction of capital, is identified: capital as a resource is characterized by physical presence, capital as potential is determined through the possibility of obtaining utility, capital as a result is expressed in some asset that has value. A new structure of intellectual capital is proposed from the perspective of the goal of capital management to ensure the growth of enterprise value.

An accounting approach to defining the concept of intellectual capital as a set of intellectual assets and intellectual property of an enterprise is presented in [12]. At the same time, the author clearly distinguishes intellectual assets into measurable (recognized in accounting) and non-measurable (not recognized in accounting). Measurable intellectual assets refer to all intangible assets of an enterprise.

Thus, in most of the works reviewed, their authors approach the definition of the concept of intellectual capital one-sidedly and do not give a clear definition of this economic concept.

Results and discussion

The emergence of the terms intellectual potential and intellectual capital is associated with changes in the practice of functioning of capital itself at the end

of the 20th and beginning of the 21st centuries. This is what the authors of [4] thought. Currently, for many enterprises, the use of labor resources is no longer limited to solving the problem of finding and using them in the production process. Today, the management of these enterprises is aware of the need to invest in the development of managerial and professional competencies of personnel in connection with the accumulation of knowledge and the introduction of innovations [7]. To measure the effectiveness of these expenses, the concept of human potential and capital first appeared, and then the intellectual potential and capital of the enterprise.

The development of the concept of intellectual capital of an enterprise has significantly expanded the opportunities for using human intellectual abilities in production activities. Previously, the production activities of enterprises were provided by a set of fixed assets used by the personnel of the enterprise in the interests of its owners, but now it is organized in a fundamentally different way. The significant difference in the organization of production activities of modern enterprises is the emergence of a new component in their capital structure - intangible assets, which essentially represent the use of intellectual capital. In addition, the distinctive characteristics of modern enterprises include the expansion of the practice of using advanced information technologies in production activities, the use of which is based on the generation of new knowledge, as well as the enhancement of managerial and professional competencies of enterprise personnel, in other words, the development of their intellectual capital [8]. At the same time, the distinctive feature of intellectual capital from the basic production assets of the enterprise is the lack of material form, as well as the fact that a certain part of it, represented by human capital, cannot be the property of the enterprise under any organizational and legal form of managing its production activities.

Based on the results of the study, we will formulate a refined definition of the intellectual capital of an enterprise, which corresponds to the modern objective realities of organizing the production activities of enterprises. It can be presented in the following form.

The intellectual capital of an enterprise should be understood as the totality of its structural components (personnel, social and organizational capital), which is in continuous development based on increasing managerial and professional competencies, expanding the practice of using modern information technologies and the constant generation of new knowledge.

In modern conditions, the development of an enterprise's intellectual capital ensures an increase in its competitiveness, an increase in the efficiency of production activities and further development by reducing the negative impact of sanctions restrictions.

Conclusion

Based on the results obtained during the research, the following conclusions can be formulated.

1. The emergence of new challenges in the global economy has entailed the need to develop a new paradigm for its development in the conditions of a changed objective reality. The key factors in this process were intellectual capital, the generation of new knowledge and the expansion of areas of practical application of information technology.

2. Since in the conditions of informatization and digitalization of the economy, intellectual capital has become a relatively new form of manifestation of an enterprise's capital, at present a clear definition of this concept has not yet been formed in scientific theory and economic practice.

3. It has been established that there are quite a lot of foreign and domestic studies, the authors of which offer different approaches to defining the concept of intellectual capital, its structuring and presentation of its essential content. However, in most of them the concept of intellectual capital is not fully disclosed.

4. Based on the analysis of modern scientific research, the authors proposed the most adequate formulation of the concept of intellectual capital to modern conditions.

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